

Entrepreneurial Opportunities of Bamboo Base Archery Sports Equipment Production in Manipur: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT: Entrepreneur is a person who accept challenging role to meet personal needs and become economically independent, capable of contributing values in both family and social life. The term “entrepreneur” is defining in a variety of ways and the concept of which is changing from time to time. Kaish and Gilad (1991) defined entrepreneurship as the process of first, discovering, and second acting on a disequilibrium opportunity.

Regarded as one of the oldest sporting event, Archery sports have been included in Olympics since the early parts of Modern Olympics. It began to attract young archers in India since 1970's but due to expensiveness, it fails to produce good archers in large number as the cost of one set of FITA bow @ recurve bows ranges from 50,000 to few lakhs.

Poor but talented archers cannot afford found good enough learning hands in bamboo bow and arrows that gradually became a good replacement for FITA bow. At this point of time, small scale Entrepreneurial works of Entrepreneurs in Archery Sports Equipment Production become a necessity.

KEY WORDS: Entrepreneurial Opportunities, FITA bow @ recurve, disequilibrium opportunity, bamboo bow and arrows.

ENTREPRENEURIAL OPPORTUNITIES

An entrepreneur is a person who continuously identifies opportunities in the market for products or services and develops new products and services to satisfy the identified needs. As an entrepreneur, one needs to visualize a successful business. Th. Ranadhir Singh (2019). The entrepreneurial abilities that one needs to develop in order to be a successful commercial Bamboo bow and Arrows producer are to seek adequate information on the art @ crafts of Bamboo bow and Arrows making and marketing opportunities. Taking calculated risk, setting a clear goal, systematic planning, commitment, persuasion and networking are important inputs for becoming a successful entrepreneur.

DEFINITION OF ENTREPRENEUR

Entrepreneur is a person who accept challenging role to meet personal needs and become economically independent, capable of contributing values in both family and social life. The term “entrepreneur” is defining in a variety of ways and the concept of which is changing from time to time. Kaish and Gilad (1991) defined entrepreneurship as the process (I) discovering, and (II) acting on a disequilibrium opportunity.

Regarded as one of the oldest sporting event, Archery sports have been included in Olympics since the early parts of Modern Olympics. It began to attract young archers in India since 1970's but due to expensiveness, it fails to produce good archers in large number as the cost of one set of FITA bow @ recurve bows ranges from 50,000 to few lakhs. On the other hand, poor but talented archers who cannot afford FITA bows found good enough learning hands in bamboo bow and arrows that gradually became a good replacement for FITA bow. At this point of time, small scale **Entrepreneurial works of Entrepreneurs in Archery Sports Equipment Production became a necessity.**

WHAT IS AN ARCHERY SPORT ALL ABOUT?

Propelling arrows from bows is called archery in peace time global world. From Long Bow to sophisticated modern bows, it takes long era till 1600 A.D. The early man use bow and arrows for hunting in the beginning. The Egyptians used Bows and Arrows as principal weapon system at wars. They fought many battles with bowmen and their bows and arrows as principal weapon system. They overran the mighty Persians and fought many wars with nations and show their might in the world. England used mounted bowmen and their weapon system as the principal weaponry since 14th century and continued for decades. But the successful use of

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firearms in the invasion of England by the Spanish Armada relegated the weapon system of Bows and arrows as war weapons to secondary place. Its uses reduce to small scale and the Chinese use it for the last time 1860.

DEFINITION OF BAMBOO

Bamboo is a tall plant found perennially in the tropical and sub-tropical areas of the globe and around 44 species of them are found growing both in the valley and hills of Manipur. Some of the species found in Manipur are Saneibi (*Bambusa Nutans*), Khok (*Bambusa Mizorameana*), Naat (*Schizostachyum*) Munsoi Watangkhoi (*Dendrocalamus Hookeri*), Longa, Tenwa (*Neomicrocalamus Prainii*) Uein (*Dendrocalamus Longispathus*), Wamu, Unal unap (*Dendrocalamus hamiltonii*), Utang (*Bambusa tulda*), Poksang (*Schizostachyum pergracile*), Meiribop (*Dendrocalamus latiflorus*), Moubi (*Melocanna baccifera*) Liwa, Laiwa (*Chimonobambusa callosa*), Ui (*Dendrocalamus manipureanus*), Tongjiwa (*Schizostachyum fuchsianum*) etc.

TRADITIONAL CULTURAL HERITAGE OF BOW AND ARROW MAKING IN MANIPUR

Nobody knows the exact chronicle or dates to know that when the weapon system does began to exist in Manipur for the first time. But one thing is sure that it is having deep relationship with the life of meetei communities. Tradition speak that those excelling in the profession of bamboo bow making in ancient days later on known as Tensubam clan literally meaning work shed of bow and arrow making. It means people belonging to the group of people / families of bow makers are known as Tensuba and the place they dwelt Tensubam.

RITUAL BACKGROUND

Archery @ Arrow shooting from Bow @ Ten Kappa is an Indispensable part of ritual ceremonial tradition of meetei communities especially in birth rituals or first ceremony after birth. In the process of birth rituals, when the moment arrives, the maternal uncle at the advice of the conduct authority the Amaiba (priest) sanctifies himself with the water from the holy pot and offer flowers to the bow & arrows and took them, goes outside the house in the frontal lawn, there the Amaiba (priest) spelling the related invocation hymns offer flowers to the arrows then the maternal uncle starts shooting the arrows to different directions, first to the Chingkhei (East), second arrow to the Thangjing (West), third to the Wangbren (South) and fourth arrow to the Koubru (North). The process concluded with the last and fifth arrow aimed at the sky and then to the earth seeking prosperous life of the child. Then, touching the frontal door with the arrow, he enter inside the house and places the 5th arrow near the Holy Pot offering it to the Almighty God (Chingu-Nongdamba) and Goddess (Chingu-Nongdambi), the supreme god and goddess who the meetei believed determine the fate of mankind.

Then, the parents of the child offer their gratitude with Akatsen (dakhsina), a kind of ritualistic offering of cash, usually coins to the maternal uncle who in turn offer the child signifying it a blessing of wealth to the child. The same is followed by the father, mother, friends and relatives and others who come to attain the ritual blessing wishing ceremony for long life, wisdom, health, wealth and prosperity to the child (Physical realities).

ARCHERY SPORTS IN MANIPUR

In peace time global world, **Archery Sports** began to appear in the Olympics during 1900 Paris Olympics as target shooting sports where live pigeons were use as targets. It took 75 years to reach India as well as Manipur in the organize FITA (Federation International Target Archery) form. India began to organize FITA style in 1975 but being an expensive event that require imported high price bows and arrows failed to attract talented youths started with traditional long bows.

Necessity is the Mother of all Invention:

TAKE DOWN BAMBOO BOW

Previously, the beginners use Traditional Long Bows but with the invention of TAKE DOWN BAMBOO BOW by one B. Chaoba Sharma, a national level archer cum master craftsman the creation of whom has been recognize by Archery Association of India (AAI) as a rare alternative of sophisticated Olympic Round FITA (Federation De International Target Archery) Bow and Arrows vide letter no Inds / Arch. Equipt. / 2000 / 67 dated 12.2. 2000, many young archers took the profession of bamboo bow and arrow making in Manipur. The profession gets a booster when Archery Association of India introduces Indian Round Archery Competition in India only for Bamboo Bow archers. The demand for "TAKE DOWN BAMBOO BOW" & ARROWS thus increase manifold as archery became a popular sports in Manipur and India then due its cost effective and easily affordable on order.

Technical display of different parts of TAKE DOWN BAMBOO BOW

Bamboo Bow and Arrow base Archery Sports equipments making activity is becoming a demanding profession in the market as most of the beginners prefer to use a piece or two of this brand of bamboo bow. As only few are found venturing in this newly found vocation, production of quality bow and arrows in large quantity is still a challenge. They cannot face the call of the hour because at the moment, demands exceed production even in local market. Hence, the need for skill development training on bamboo bow and arrows making may be initiated to produce well train hands and skill craftsmen for this vocation.

BAMBOO SPECIES SUITABLE FOR BOW MAKING

Every species of Bamboo can be use for making bow and arrows but all are not found good for the sports. Only few species of the plant are found suitable and good for bow and arrow making. They are Saneibi (Bambusa Nutans), Naat (Schizostachyum Munsoi) Watangkhohi (Dendrocalamus Hookeri), Longa (Uein Dendrocalamus Longispathus), Wamu, Unal Unap (Dendrocalamus hamiltonii), Utang (Bambusa tulda), Tenwa (Neomicrocalamus Prainii).

SELECTION OF RAW MATERIAL

Bamboo is abundantly available in the wilds of North Eastern States of the country but all cannot be use for the purpose. Hence, selection of suitable raw material i.e bamboo species is one vital issue for production of quality bow and arrows. No doubt, bows and arrows can be carved out from any kind of bamboo but durability, effectiveness, and quality of the products is the main question for marketing purpose.

WHERE FROM THE RAW MATERIAL IS COLLECTED

The raw materials for making bows and arrows are collected from different places of North Eastern states but the best quality bow can be carved out from the bamboo species found in the treacherous terrains and hill slopes of Manipur. For arrows, the raw materials are collected from Koubru hill ranges of Manipur and Meghalaya state.

COST OF A BAMBOO PIECE AND NUMBER OF BOWS THAT CAN BE CARVED FROM

Generally, the cost of a Bamboo Tree cost Rs. 200 to 300 but including cutting, trimming and transportation charges, it shoots upto Rs 1000 / piece. Average height of a bamboo varies from 10 to 15 mts and the usable length too differs from one piece to another.

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But, limbs of bows can be cut out as per the average arm length of the beginners belonging to different age groups keeping in mind the length of hands and heights of the targeted users.

COST OF A SET OF BAMBOO BOW & ARROWS

At present, the cost of a set of Bamboo Bow & Arrows ranges from Rs. 5,000/-to Rs 6,000/- and it is within the easily affordable range of prices. The Entrepreneurs who are in the field of bamboo bow and arrow making entrepreneurial profession appeal the state government to look into the positive aspect of bow and arrow making. It is so because, to meet the ever increasing demand of these equipments, a large scale bamboo base sports equipment production industry will do justice. It will help generating employment opportunities for both the educated and uneducated unemployed youths of the region.

MARKET OF BAMBOO BOWS THE TAKE DOWN

Being a light weight, easy to carry, packable, detachable and assemblage item with little risk, it has nationwide market like Archery sports clubs & associations, non residential & residential schools, sports academies, defense establishments, railways, services located across the nation.

BENEFITS

It is ecofriendly sports equipment that can be purchased at an easily manageable price. Maximum part of the bamboo bows and arrows are bio degradable and can be reuse as fuel woods after they are broken or exhausted from further use in archery sports. Generally, a find archer use to carry spare limbs and arrows during practice and competition also to manage the event if equipment related problem arises with the one in use during competition hours.

Thanks You All

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